

Mother as first line of defense against intestinal disorders among babies of tropical countries

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Introduction

Mother is the gift of god , it bears a lot of works and perform many duties mainly in rural and non civilized areas in comparison to urban areas where life is very complicated , has a rapid rhythm and most of mothers spent their day time in work place whether its company , factory or even school , they let their young babies in less comfortable and poor hygiene nurseries or in their relatives house whether the grandfather or grandmother of the baby is very busy with cooking, washing of clothes and cleaning ,then they allow to the baby to play on ground and contaminate him/herself with waste present on the ground , sucking their fingers , dirty and long nails also contact with domestic animals ,cats ,dogs , goats and other animals , which is usually stay free in the yard .

Most of abdominal disorders occur among babies of workers mothers due to insufficient care of mothers to their babies.

UnFournately most of tropical countries are poor , that means many children are malnourished and then their

immune system is very weak due to their age and nutrition status , that induce loss of millions of children in that countries due to poverty and lack of health education among natives of that countries .

Literacy have no real value in tropical countries particularly among workers mothers due to absence of their sufficient role toward their babies, then they spent more time in work and more money in health care units to treat their ill baby .

In comparison to urban worker mothers, the rural mothers take more cores to their babies and feed them healthy foods and drinks such as cows and goats milks and natural fruits and vegetables from their farms that lead to stronger body of rural babies in comparison to weak and malnourished urban baby.

Misunderstanding of civilization in most of developing tropical countries leads to a lot of socioeconomical and health problems which is very clear among less than 5 years age group, certainly those of workers mothers in civilized areas[1-2].

Fig.1: Healthy children need healthy mothers

Community role is very important to save the life of those neglected children, to enable them to enjoy with healthy and happy life also the role of international organizations and nongovernmental organization is very important, when we save children we save the generation of tomorrow.

Lastly I think that mother is the corner stone of the healthy and modern community and all efforts should be used to improve their health and their life style.

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Reference

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